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**19th International Conference
on Chemistry and the Environment**
Belgrade, Serbia, June 8-12, 2025

Environmental Chemistry for Sustainability

E-Book of Abstracts

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**19th International Conference on Chemistry
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E-Book of Abstracts

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Dear participants, welcome to Belgrade!

On behalf of the Division of Chemistry and the Environment (DCE) (<https://www.euchems.eu/divisions/chemistry-and-the-environment-2/>) of the European Association of the Chemical Societies (EuChemS) (<https://www.euchems.eu/>), the Serbian Chemical Society (<https://www.shd.org.rs/en/>), and the local organizing committee, it is our great pleasure and privilege to warmly welcome you to the 19th International Conference on Chemistry and the Environment (ICCE 2025).

This prestigious event, which gathers nearly 350 participants from across the globe is hosted by the Serbian Chemical Society with the support of the University of Belgrade and the University of Novi Sad.

At a time when continued scientific progress is essential to ensure a healthy environment and a sustainable future, ICCE 2025 addresses key challenges and emerging developments, advances knowledge and inspires action through the lens of Environmental Chemistry. In addition to the main program running in fourteen parallel sessions, ICCE 2025 will feature four pre-conference satellite events, each dedicated to current research priorities and strategic environmental topics and EuChemS DCE Career Award lecture by Terry Frank Bidleman from Sweden. The scientific program includes seven plenary lectures including two Distinguished Lectures from the American Chemical Society, and fourteen keynote lectures that introduce parallel sessions, comprising 175 oral and 156 poster presentations. A Special Editorial Panel Discussion, with editors from leading international scientific journals, will provide valuable insight into the evolving landscape of scientific publishing.

ICCE 2025 provides an excellent platform for networking, exchange of ideas and collaboration. Our collective mission is to deepen understanding of pollutant's cycling, and their fate and effects in the environment, while advancing pollution prevention and waste management. The latest developments in environmental analysis, pollution monitoring and risk assessment directly impact societal response to environmental challenges, which inevitably focus on various sustainability strategies. To be effective, these responses must be supported by excellent knowledge-based tools and societal inspiration, both offered by ICCE 2025.

We hope that you will not only enjoy the rich scientific program but also take-home memorable experiences from Serbia!

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Special thanks to the Evertéa Foundation, which generously provided registration grants to a number of students and early-career researchers from around the world who would otherwise not have had the opportunity to attend. Additionally, the best oral and poster presentations will be recognized and awarded by the Local Organizing Committee, with Springer eBook vouchers as prizes.

Roland Kallenborn, EuChemS DCE Chairman, Antonio Marcomini, previous ICCE 2023 Chairman and Philippe Garrigues, Editor-in-Chief of *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* provided us with valuable guidance in shaping the format and structure of this year's conference in line with the ICCE tradition. The input of all EuChemS DCE members was instrumental in refining the scientific program, selecting invited speakers, and ensuring a robust and fair abstract review process. We deeply appreciate the support of our colleagues from partner associations as George Cobb, John Giesy and Virender Kumar Sharma from Division on Environmental Chemistry of the American Chemical Society (ACSEnv), Roberto Terzano, Hemda Garelick and Melanie Kah from International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) and Takeshi Nakano from Japan Society for Environmental Chemistry for helping us to make this event remarkable.

Company "Congrexpo" d.o.o., our professional conference organizer, led by Mrs. Olivera Popović, manages all logistics and technical coordination with dedication and professionalism. The Hotel M team, under the direction of Mrs. Jelena Jakovljević, ensures a welcoming and pleasant experience for all participants in the warm and familiar setting of one of Belgrade's most established congress venues. A very special "thank you" goes to our volunteers Slaven Tenodi, Tijana Marijanović, Sanja Vasiljević, Dušan Rakić, Marija Simić, Katarina Stojanović, Marija Kovačević, Ana Lazić, and Lazar Popović.

We thank all the participants for their oral and poster presentations which make the ICCE2025 shining!

Professor Ivana Ivančev-Tumbas,
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Leveraging biochars and hydrochars for effective sequestration and biodegradation of organophosphorus pesticides

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With the global population projected to grow by 70–100% over the next 30 years, meeting the corresponding increase in food demand will leave minimal room for yield losses. Crop threats, responsible for up to 40% of yield losses, make reliance on agrochemicals essential to sustain production. Among these, organophosphorus pesticides (OPPs) constitute 33% of the global pesticide market (approximately 750 kilotons annually) and are widely used for their broad-spectrum activity, chemical stability, high efficiency, and low cost. However, their mobility, persistence, and toxicity—combined with the fact that up to 90% of pesticides fail to reach their biological targets—pose a significant risk to groundwater systems, the primary source of drinking water [1]. To address this issue, modifying infiltration media with appropriate amendments to promote the immobilization and/or biodegradation of OPPs offers a promising solution [2]. With the goal of testing this approach, three sets of single-component batch systems were set up over 50 days. These systems consisted of the alluvial sediment of the Danube River, a selected OPP (fenthion, fenitrothion, malathion, or parathion-methyl; initial amount: 174 to 519 µg/kg) and an organic amendment (application rate: 0.5 w/w%): either biochar (BC; two variants) or hydrochar (HTC; six variants). Both BCs and HTCs were produced from biomass residues of miscanthus and sugar beet shreds, processed at 400°C and 180, 200, and 220°C, respectively. The three experimental setups included sediment amended with selected: (I) BC or HTC, (II) BC or HTC inoculated with the *Bacillus megaterium* strain (BD5; isolated from the sediment used), and (III) BC or HTC inoculated with the BD5 strain and biostimulated with a mineral medium. Each setup was complemented by a control trial, differing only by the absence of the selected BC or HTC, with all other constituents (i.e., BD5 strain and mineral medium; application rate: 1 mL/mg) remaining present. After the 50-day period, residual OPP amounts were quantified and compared with initial values, leading to the following general conclusions. In control trials, OPP reductions of 61–90% were observed, likely due to abiotic processes and biodegradation by the native microorganisms in the sediment sample. The addition of BCs or HTCs resulted in increased residual OPPs, indicating enhanced sequestration (i.e., adsorption) onto the applied materials (malathion < fenthion < fenitrothion < parathion-methyl, and HTCs < BCs). Compared to amendments, inoculated BCs and HTCs demonstrated a stronger capacity for OPPs removal (particularly evident for fenitrothion and parathion-methyl), suggesting the involvement of biofilm-induced biodegradation. Finally, biostimulation with a mineral medium further promoted the biodegradation activity of inoculated BCs and HTCs. Since the tested BCs and HTCs improved OPPs retention in all setups relative to the sediment used and promoted biodegradation in inoculated trials, it is clear that their utilization could significantly aid in mitigating groundwater contamination by OPPs.

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